

Cooling-rate Independent PEEK Composites via OATMEAL for High-Rate Processing

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Thermoplastic Composite Manufacturing: Need for Speed

High Cooling Rates in AFP: Increased Voids and Reduced Primary Crystallization

Kirchhoff, Joseph G. and Heathman, Nathaniel T. and Yap, Timothy and Koirala, Pratik and Hudson, Tyler and Tehrani, Mehran, **Interlaminar Bonding in Thermoplastic Composites: A Comparative Analysis of Laser Afp and Post-Processing**. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4955051>

Fusion Bonding in Thermoplastic Composites

Crystallinity in Thermoplastics Actually Inhibits Interdiffusion

Boiko et al., **Healing of interfaces of amorphous and semi-crystalline polyethylene terephthalate in the vicinity of the glass transition temperature**, Polymer (2001)

How can we leverage amorphous bonding for high-speed manufacturing?

Fig. 2. Shear strength as a function of healing temperature at amorphous/amorphous and crystalline/crystalline PET ($M_0 = 15\,000$) interfaces. Healing time is 30 min.

Exploring Amorphous Bonding: A Preliminary Investigation

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Two-Step Experimental Plan

Materials

- Low Melt PAEK™ (LM-PAEK), with 55% fiber volume fraction, supplied by Toray (TC1125)
- Polyetherimide (PEI, Ultem 1000), supplied from piezopvdf as a neat polymer 5-micron film

Both Steps Were Done in a Vacuum Bag Only Setting

PEI Thickness (μm)	Step Two Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) – 30 mins
5	230
10	280
15	360
20	

*Melt Temperature of LM-PAEK (305 $^{\circ}\text{C}$)

All bagging materials supplied by Airtech

Amorphous Bonding: Unlocking Processing Below Melt Point

SBS normalized in respect to National Institute for Aviation Research (NIAR). (2020, February 21). *CAM-RP-2019-036 Rev NC*. Wichita State University.

PEI-PEEK Tape + Laser Ablation (OATMEAL)

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OATMEAL is Engineered to be Cooling-rate Agnostic

The added amorphous polymer enables sub-melt consolidation (without losing crystalline history)

Why OATMEAL?

$$T_{\text{melt PEEK}} > T > T_{\text{g PEI}}$$

- Amorphous polymer
 - Semi-crystalline polymer
 - Fiber
- Interlayer
(Resin-rich)

Laser Ablate Excess PEI to Improve Performance

(a)

(b)

(c)

Performance improves after laser ablation

Crystallinity Measurements

AFM-IR Shows Us that PEI Interdiffuses ~25-30 Microns

Schematic from: Mathurin et al., “Advanced Infrared Nanospectroscopy Using Photothermal Induced Resonance Technique, AFMIR: New Approach Using Tapping Mode” (2020)

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Recent Publications:

- 1) “In situ consolidation of carbon fiber PAEK via laser-assisted automated fiber placement”, Heathman et al., Composites Part B (2023)
- 2) “Resin percolation and intimate contact in fast processing of thermoplastic composites”, Kirchhoff et al., Composite Part A (2024)
- 3) “Interlaminar Bonding in Thermoplastic Composites: A Comparative Analysis of Laser AFP and Post-Processing”, Kirchhoff et al., SSRN (2024)
- 4) “Experimental Evaluation of the In-Situ Consolidation Automated Fiber Placement of Polyaryletherketone Composites”, Grimsley, Hudson et al., Thermoplastics Composites Conference (2024)
- 5) “Feasibility of Amorphous Bonding in Thermoplastic Composites and the Resulting Interlaminar Residual Stresses”, Kirchhoff, Hudson, Tehrani, SAMPE (2025)